

RESEARCH PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

An ecofriendly approach for removal of oil contaminated soil: A biosurfactant study

P. Nithiya^{*1}, M. Hemalatha¹, S. Thevasundari¹, C Thilagavathi¹, R. Mohandoss²,
B. Rajeswari³

¹Department of Botany, Seethalakshmi Ramaswami College, Tiruchirappalli, India

²Department of Biotechnology, Maruthupandiyar College, Thanjavur, India

³Department of Science and Humanities, Shivani College of Engineering, Tiruchirappalli, India

Key words: Bioremediation, DNA, Oil sludge

<http://dx.doi.org/10.12692/ijb/25.6.448-453>

Article published on December 10, 2024

Abstract

Oil sludge which is entrapped within soil where its spills. It causes serious problems to the environment as well as both animal and human who interact with them. The hydrocarbons in the sludge penetrate from the top soil into the subsoil slowly, presenting a direct risk of contamination to subsoil and groundwater. On the other hand, the light hydrocarbons in the oil sludge vaporize, leaving behind a layer of oil containing dust of soil which blows upwards to pollute the air. Therefore, the oil sludge should be treated to prevent harm to environment. In this present study, oil contaminated soil was taken for the research work. The soil samples were isolated and their growth characteristics, DNA isolation and DNA estimation was done by using electrophoresis and diphenylamine method. From the results the growth characteristics and DNA quantification confirms that *Bacillus subtilis* will act as a good surfactant and ecofriendly microorganism. This study will enhance the growth of biosurfactant (bioremediation) for our sustainable environment.

*Corresponding Author: P. Nithiya ✉ nithypappu@gmail.com

Introduction

Microorganisms can only alter the speciation of metal contaminant and convert them into nontoxic forms (Lovley, 1997). Recent advances in the field of microbial surfactants are largely attributed to the development of quick, reliable methods for screening biosurfactant-producing microbes and assessing their potential (Desai, 1997).

Van der (Vegt *et al.*, 1991) developed an asymmetric drop shape analysis by profile for the assessment of potential biosurfactant-producing bacteria. A list of industrially important biosurfactants produced by microorganisms is given in Table 1. Out of all these, three biosurfactants sophorolipids, surfactin and rhamnolipids are most important biosurfactants, which are studied, in detail in this work.

While bioventing has been shown to remove soil pollutants ranging from light to middle distillate oil (Lee and Swindoll, 1993; Mosco and Zytner, 2017). Most remediation experts believe the most effective remediation method will depend on the type of oil spilled, quantity spilled, and the environmental medium impacted (Samanta *et al.*, 2002; Pugazhendhi *et al.*, 2018). The aim of this work is design after number of literature survey done and to remove oil from contaminated soil for oil free environment.

Materials and methods

The samples were collected from oil contaminated areas such as, petrol bunk, Automobile workshop (Tractor workshop), oil mill, and Engine pump set around Thanjavur district. The sample was collected in a sterile polyethylene bag with the help of sterile tea spoon and it was taken to the laboratory immediately and analyzed for the isolation of biosurfactant producing bacteria (Fig. 1).

Isolation of bacterial species from soil samples

Bacterial species were isolated from the collected soil samples by serial dilution and agar plating method. The soil sample was diluted from 10^{-1} to 10^{-6} dilutions, and the diluted soil samples were spread on sterile nutrient agar plates.

Fig. 1. Soil samples

pH

The isolates (1ml each) were inoculated into six tubes of 10 ml nutrient broth of varying pH values (6, 7 and 8). NaOH (1M) and HCl (1M) were used to adjust the pH in the broths. The tubes were then incubated at 37°C for 160 hours, after which the cultures were analysed for further analyses.

Growth characteristics

The inoculated microbes on the selective medium are tend to grow during the incubation period from 24 hours to 48 hours at 22°C. The growth is observed and the colony morphology is interpreted. The bioluminescent bacteria give a characteristic circular, rod shaped colony with white translucent appearance.

Molecular analysis - DNA isolation

The old nutrient broth culture is transferred into fresh nutrient broth. Then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours in shaker. On the next day, 1.5 ml of grown culture was taken in a centrifuge tube and centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 5 minutes. Supernatant was discarded and pellet was suspended in 100 µl of CTAB and 20µl of 10% SDS added and vortex mixing. The tube is placed in a water bath at 65°C for 15 minutes. Equal volume of phenol: chloroform (1:1 ratio) was added and vortexes. Centrifuge 8000 rpm for 10 minutes. Collect the supernatant and add 100 µl of ice cold ethanol and mixed vortexes. Centrifuged 8000 rpm for 10 minutes and air dried for 15 minutes, and ethanol in discarded. Then add 15µl of 1X TAE buffer stored in refrigerator at 4°C. Then the stored DNA will be electrophoresis.

Agarose gel electrophoresis

Electrophoresis is the technique used to separate and sometimes purify macromolecules especially proteins and nucleic acids. 0.8% of agarose gel was prepared in 1X TAE buffer ethidium bromide (1µg /M) was added into it and heated till Agarose gel fully suspended. The gel was cooled up to 55°C and casted in casting unit of electrophoresis assembly. The gel was run at 50 V for 30 minutes to equilibrate. The 9µl of isolated DNA sample was mixed with 2 µl of gel loading dye. 10 µl of mixture was loaded into wells and run at 80-100 V for 30 minutes.

Quantitative analysis of genomic DNA

To estimate the DNA, a convenient and easy method is colorimeter method, which is based on the quantitative reaction of deoxy sugar with the diphenylamine reagent. 1.0g of diphenylamine dissolved in 97.5ml of glacial acidic acid and added

2.5ml of concentrated sulphuric acid and stored in a room temperature. The 5ml of diphenylamine reagent was mixed with 0.5ml solution containing nucleic acid. The mixture was showed on a boiling water bath for 5 minutes. It was then estimated at 595 nm against blank. The blank was prepared with 0.5ml of distilled water once 5ml of a reagent in water both for 5 minutes and cooled. Absorbance was read out at 595 nm using UV spectrophotometer.

Results and discussion

The present study was conducted to determine the oil degrading activity of biosurfactant producing organism and all the isolated strains were screened for the confirmation of bio surfactant producing bacteria is *Bacillus subtilis* and the strains showed good result finally that strains taken for the further study.

Table 1. Industrially important biosurfactants produced by microorganisms

Biosurfactant	Organisms	Reference(s)
Glycolipids		
Sphorolipids	<i>T. bombicola</i> ; <i>T. apicola</i> ; <i>T. petrophilum</i>	Tulloch <i>et al.</i> , 1962; Spenser <i>et al.</i> , 1970; Inoue and Ito 1982; Asmer <i>et al.</i> , 1988; Cavelero and Cooper, 2003; Daverey and Pakshirajan, 2010
Rhamnolipids	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> ; <i>Pseudomonas</i> sp <i>Serratia rubidea</i>	Jarvis and Johnson, 1949; Reiling <i>et al.</i> , 1986; Matsufuji <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Wu <i>et al.</i> , 2007; Sarachat <i>et al.</i> , 2010
Trehalolipids	<i>R. erythropolis</i> , <i>N. erythropolis</i>	Rapp <i>et al.</i> , 1979; Uchida <i>et al.</i> , 1989
Lipopeptides		
Surfactin	<i>B. subtilis</i> ; <i>B. pumilus</i>	Arima <i>et al.</i> , 1968; Kakinuma <i>et al.</i> , 1969; Cooper <i>et al.</i> , 1981; Makkar and Cameotra, 1998; Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2009
Viscosin	<i>P. fluorescens</i>	Neu and Poralla, 1990
Gramicidins	<i>B. brevis</i>	Marahiel <i>et al.</i> , 1977
Polymyxins	<i>B. polymyxa</i>	Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 1965; Falagas <i>et al.</i> , 2005
Glycolipids		
Fatty acids, Phospholipids and Neutral lipids		
Fatty acids	<i>A. parafineus</i> ; <i>C. lepus</i> ; <i>P. spiculisporum</i>	Cooper <i>et al.</i> , 1989; Makkar and Cameotra, 2002
Neutral lipids	<i>N. erythropolis</i>	McDonald <i>et al.</i> , 1981
Phospholipids	<i>T. thioxidans</i>	Beeba <i>et al.</i> , 1971; Lemke <i>et al.</i> , 1995
Polymeric surfactants		
Emulsan	<i>A. calcoaceticus</i>	Zosim <i>et al.</i> , 1982; Rosenberg <i>et al.</i> , 1993
Biodispersan	<i>A. calcoaceticus</i>	Rosenberg <i>et al.</i> , 1988
Mannan-lipid -protein	<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	Kappeli <i>et al.</i> , 1984
Liposan	<i>Candida lipolytica</i>	Cirigliano and Carman, 1985
Carbohydrate protein lipid	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	Desai <i>et al.</i> , 1988
Particulate biosurfactants		
Vesicles and fimbriae	<i>A. calcoaceticus</i>	Gutnick and Shabtai, 1987
Whole cells	Variety of bacteria	Fattom and Shilo, 1985

Table 2. Colony morphology of nutrient agar

SL	Sample	Colony morphology on nutrient agar
1	Petrol bunk soil	Smooth whitish pin pointed colony
2	Tractor work shop soil	Smooth whitish pin pointed colony
3	Oil mill soil	Smooth whitish pin pointed colony
4	Engine oil soil	Smooth whitish pin pointed colony

Characterization of isolated bacteria

Colony morphology: The shape, size, elevation, margin and cooler of the colony were observed in the culture plates with Nutrient Agar used as the nutrient medium. The observations were noted down (Table 2).

Fig. 2C. Growth study of *Bacillus subtilis* pH 8

The effect of temperature, pH and salinity on surface activity and emulsification index has been shown in (Fig. 2A, 1B & 1C), respectively. The results were comparable to that obtained for *B. subtilis*. The surface activity of the biosurfactant remained stable over the range of

temperature and pH, studied. With respect to pH, the least surface tension was obtained from neutral pH, onwards. Such extreme stability was also reported by Abdel-Mawgoud *et al.*, 2009 and Gandhimathi *et al.*, 2009 for the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strain and *Brevibacterium aureum* MSA13 respectively. This suggests that the biosurfactant isolated may be used in microbial enhanced oil recovery processes where high temperatures prevail. The findings indicate the potential application of the biosurfactant over a wide range of temperature and pH. This finds application in situations where extreme conditions of temperature and pH prevail such as bioremediation of soil as well as marine environments. It can also be used for enhanced oil recovery operations.

In this present study, initially the growth pattern by the isolates on relatively simple hydrocarbon source (engine oil) was studied. Mitchell, 1965 has reported that growth can be taken as a parameter for microbial utilization of substrate. Eventually screening that about Arabinose, Salicin, Trebulose, Cellobiose, Maltose, Lactose, Sucrose, Fructose and Glucose carbon content of hydrocarbons present as bacterial protoplasm.

The ability of a surfactant to enhance the biodegradation of slightly soluble organic compounds depends on the extent to which it increases the bioavailability of the compound. Research has demonstrated that biosurfactants exhibit versatile properties such as excellent self-organization, protein-binding and antitumor action, Harvest the synthetic surfactants synthetic do have the properties which end up in causing a high environmental impact Mukherjee, 2006. In the present study, the partially purified biosurfactant exhibited maximum emulsification activity and decay constant when compared to other commercially available surfactants thus proving its efficiency. The estimation of DNA results were presented in the Table 3 and Fig. 2D.

Table 3. DNA Estimation by diphenylamine method

Sl Particulars	B	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	T1	T2	T3	T4
1 Volume of standard(ml)	—	0.4	0.8	1.2	1.6	2.0	—	—	—	—
2 Concentration of standard(ml)	—	40	80	120	160	200	—	—	—	—
3 Volume of test sample(ml)	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
4 Volume of perchloric acid(ml)	2	1.6	1.2	0.8	0.4	—	—	—	—	—
5 Volume of diphenylamine(ml)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
6 Absorbance of DNA estimation 630nm										
7 Optical density	0.00	0.454	0.479	0.434	0.418	0.479	0.573	0.825	0.019	0.020

Fig. 2D. DNA estimation by diphenylamine method

The bacterial isolates viz. *Bacillus subtilis* were screened as hydrocarbon utilizers as they were capable of growing in petrol bunk soil in this present study. Members of the genus *Rhodococcus* are HC degraders Van Hamme, 2003. *Pseudomonas species*, ubiquitous in soil and water are of considerable scientific and technological importance and comprise a taxon of metabolically versatile organism capable of utilizing a wide range of simple and complex organic compound. Molecular techniques for the identification of hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria have been rarely used in environmental studies Chang, 2001 and Roling, 2002.

Conclusion

Eco-friendly technologies must be used to clean the environment such as degradation by microorganisms. Bioremediation has been accepted as an important method for the treatment of oil pollution by biosurfactant produced by bacterial colonies. Under certain conditions, living microorganisms primarily bacteria can metabolize various classes of hydrocarbons compound. The results suggest that *Bacillus subtilis* is a good

producer of biosurfactant and against hydrocarbon contaminated places. Thereby the oil contaminated soils can be degraded by introducing the biosurfactant producing organisms such as *Bacillus subtilis*, which is able to degrade the oil contaminated soil from the environment. This study has to be taken for further research for betterment work.

References

- Abdel-Mawgoud AM, Aboulwafa MM, Hassouna NAH.** 2009. Characterization of rhamnolipid produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolate Bs20. Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology **157**(2), 329–345.
- Chang W, Jones TN, Holoman TP.** 2001. Anaerobic polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH)-degrading enrichment cultures under methanogenic conditions. In Sixth International In Situ and On-Site Bioremediation Symposium, 205–209.
- Desai JD, Banat IM.** 1997. Microbial production of surfactants and their commercial potential. Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews **61**(1), 47–64.
- Gandhimathi R, Kiran GS, Hema TA, Selvin J, Raviji TR, Shanmughapriya S.** 2009. Production and characterization of lipopeptide biosurfactant by a sponge-associated marine actinomycetes *Nocardioopsis alba* MSA10. Bioprocess and Biosystems Engineering **32**(6), 825–835.
- Lee MD, Swindoll CM.** 1993. Bioventing for in situ remediation. Hydrological Sciences Journal **38**(4), 273–282.

- Lovley DR, Coates JD.** 1997. Bioremediation of metal contamination. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology* **8**(3), 285–289.
- Mitchell R, Nevo Z.** 1965. Decomposition of structural polysaccharides of bacteria by marine microorganisms. *Nature* **205**(4975), 1007.
- Mosco MJ, Zytner RG.** 2017. Large-scale bioventing degradation rates of petroleum hydrocarbons and determination of scale-up factors. *Bioremediation Journal* **21**(3–4), 149–162.
- Mukherjee S, Das P, Sen R.** 2006. Towards commercial production of microbial surfactants. *Trends in Biotechnology* **24**(11), 509–515.
- Pugazhendhi A, Ranganathan K, Kaliannan T.** 2018. Biosorptive removal of copper (II) by *Bacillus cereus* isolated from contaminated soil of electroplating industry in India. *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution* **229**, 1–9.
- Roling WF, Milner MG, Jones DM, Lee K, Daniel F, Swannell RJ, Head IM.** 2002. Robust hydrocarbon degradation and dynamics of bacterial communities during nutrient-enhanced oil spill bioremediation. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* **68**(11), 5537–5548.
- Samanta SK, Singh OV, Jain RK.** 2002. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons: environmental pollution and bioremediation. *Trends in Biotechnology* **20**(6), 243–248.
- Van der Vegt W, Van der Mei HC, Noordmans J, Busscher HJ.** 1991. Assessment of bacterial biosurfactant production through axisymmetric drop shape analysis by profile. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* **35**(6), 766–770.
- Van Hamme JD, Singh A, Ward OP.** 2003. Recent advances in petroleum microbiology. *Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews* **67**(4), 503–549.